

AI-based recommender for sustainable tourism (FKZ 67KI21005)

Summary of the findings

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AIR - AI-based recommender for sustainable tourism: Summary of the findings

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1 Project objectives

AIR is a joint project for the research and development of digital visitor management in tourism destinations. The aim of the project is to conduct application-oriented research into design options for innovative solutions for future-oriented visitor management using AI technology.

The core contents of the project are

- **Digital visitor measurement and smart sensors:** By equipping the pilot destinations with local and global sensor technology, large quantities of measurement data are produced, analysed and made available (→ work package 1)
- **Open data and data hubs:** Storage and exchange of data on open data hubs and initiation of exchange formats (→ work packages 2 and 5)
- **AI-based modelling:** use of machine learning algorithms to predict visit frequencies and identify PoI alternatives (→ work package 3)
- **Management of digital touchpoints:** Use of digital (and analogue) touchpoints for the communication of frequency and prediction data (→ work package 4)
- **Smart destinations:** Identification of comparable projects and integration potentials for smart destinations (→ work package 5).

AIR is the first comprehensive research project on visitor management outside of large protected areas. While there is usually a legal basis for the purpose of protection in large protected areas, this is lacking in tourism destinations outside protected areas. Accordingly, the motivations and responsibilities of users and providers are different (Figure 1)

The project was active from 1 January 2022 to 31 January 2024. During this period, the project partners were in active dialogue with the academic and destination practice community during the project period with their own webinars, at conferences and in scientific and popular publications. The link to destination practice in particular was an integral part of the project: using use cases in different types of destinations, the aim was to generate empirical data on visitor management through surveys and intervention studies.

Figure 1: Different perspectives on the topic of visitor management

Source: Reif, J., Schmücker, D., Naschert, L., & Horster, E. (2024). Visitor Management in Tourism Destinations: Current Challenges in Measuring and Managing Visitors' Spatio-Temporal Behaviour. In M. Pillmayer, M. Hansen, & M. Karl (Eds.), *Tourism Destination Development: A Geographic Perspective on Destination Management and Tourist Demand* (pp. 81-104). De Gruyter.

2 Project partners and project setup

Two types of collaborative partners are active in the project: R&D collaborative partners work in work packages 1 to 6, which focus on research and solution development in the respective core topics.

Destination partners, in turn, represent the practical application perspective as destination management organisations (DMO): the six use cases of work package 7 bring together the threads of R&D work packages 1 to 6. This should ensure that no developments are made "at the green table", but that the destination partners can specifically address the problems in their destination.

The eighth work package relates to project management, in particular for the network coordinator NIT.

The following partners were involved:

- R&D alliance partners:
 - Kiel University of Applied Sciences (work package 3)
 - West Coast University of Applied Sciences, Heide (work packages 1 and 5)
 - Kempten University of Applied Sciences: (work packages 3 and 7, together with Füssen Tourismus)
 - Institute for Tourism and Spa Research in Northern Europe (NIT), Kiel: (work packages 6 and 8)
 - Outdooractive AG, Immenstadt (work packages 2 and 4)
- Destination partners (all work package 7)
 - Füssen Tourism and Marketing AöR
 - North Sea Tourism Service GmbH
 - Ruhr Tourismus GmbH
 - Sauerland Tourismus e.V.
 - Tourism Agency Lübeck Bay AöR
 - Winter Sports Arena Sauerland/Siegerland-Wittgenstein e. V.

In summary, this results in a matrix organisation: all six use cases pass through the development steps of work packages 1 to 6 or make use of their research and development capacities (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Network partners and work packages

3 Summary of findings

In this project, we were able to demonstrate the challenges associated with a digital visitor management system in tourist destinations.

We have divided this last chapter into three core results (organisation, technology, visitors), one methodological result (intervention research) and an outlook.

3.1 Organisation

This was the first project in the German-speaking world to analyse digital visitor management outside of large protected areas on a large scale. Large protected areas are often "controlled destinations": they can be easily demarcated, are centrally managed (often with unlimited management control over the area) and are subject to strict regulations (e.g. rules on use and access). Visitors can also be expected to have a minimum interest in nature and the landscape. This is generally not the case for tourism destinations outside of large protected areas.

The first challenge identified in the project therefore does not relate to technology or visitors, but to the organisational conditions in a tourism destination: the experiences of the use case managers in this project show quite clearly that there were sometimes considerable obstacles to cooperation with both administrations and other tourism organisations, which could not be completely overcome in the course of the project. In some cases, the installation of local sensor technology was not possible in the form originally planned because infrastructure operators or municipalities stood in the way of implementation (in comparison, cooperation with private stakeholders was comparatively easy). Changing priorities among partners within the destination can also lead to implementation difficulties.

In future projects, a precise problem analysis should be carried out and then sufficient time (two years or more) should be allowed for installation planning and implementation and the land and infrastructure owners should be involved in the planning phase. Alternatively, depending on the objective of the visitor measurement, global sensor technology can be used (see next section).

3.2 Technology

The second group of challenges relates to the technology used. In addition to the difficulties associated with the lengthy installation of local sensors, it also became clear that the sensors need to be calibrated in order to prevent drift in the data. This drift occurs when small measurement errors add up over time and then lead to implausible utilisation rates. In addition, data gaps are always to be expected.

Interesting results were achieved in the project using global sensors (i.e. location data from mobile devices, data from long-range smartphone apps or specific digital solutions such as data from car

park apps). However, this data is still quite complex to obtain and limited in terms of spatial and temporal resolution. It was not possible to work with transaction data in this project. It also became clear that new insights can be gained by combining local and global data.

Although the use of local sensor technology is suitable for digital visitor management, the costs and benefits are often not in a favourable ratio (technical challenges and socio-political acceptance). The use of big data (global sensor technology) such as mobile location events is promising, but a wide range of analysis options are generally not available on a daily basis or in real time.

Forecast data must be reliable for deployment, otherwise the applications will not be accepted by the stakeholders on site. Experience-based applications can be an efficient and cost-effective alternative for some areas of visitor management. In the project, it became clear that local experts generally have such a good knowledge of the conditions that they are able to forecast the expected capacity utilisation or demand volume in relation to calendar days and depending on the expected weather.

Given the complexity of data procurement and data structures, it seems tempting to rely on the human factor. However, intuition and local knowledge are not always a substitute for measurement data: Neither automated visitor guidance nor longer-term forecasting nor targeted performance measurement is possible with it (see below: Intervention-based performance measurement). Sensor technology is therefore a basic prerequisite for data-driven visitor and therefore also destination management.

We can also take away from the technical developments that the modelling of forecasts and alternatives is a destination-specific task and cannot be easily exchanged between destination types. Random forest and XGBoost models have often proven to be the best choice for forecasting purposes.

3.3 Visitors

The third group of challenges in the implementation of digital visitor management concerns the perception, behaviour and accessibility of visitors.

We have found that the perception of "full" can differ depending on the PoI and the person. This is significant because this perception is also important for the relevance of utilisation information, as visitors only react to interventions if they are relevant. However, this is rarely the case with predominantly selective utilisation and overloading at PoIs.

The behavioural economic effect of displaying crowdsourced information and recommendations is not easy to predict. The steering effects are often small or non-existent. However, there are also indications of an opposite effect from the research data in the digital space: labelling a PoI as highly frequented makes it even more interesting. However, these effects are also small and need to be replicated.

We can also see from the data that information and nudging are often too weak as forms of intervention. A significant steering effect through information or nudging is not to be expected with only low visitor pressure: A stable mindset of visitors usually requires more robust influence, e.g. reservation and advance booking. The extent to which the introduction of dynamic pricing actually has a steering effect (or whether a producer surplus is simply skimmed off) cannot be answered from this project.

3.4 Intervention research

In this project, we attempted to implement an intervention-based research logic: In field experiments, defined factors were changed in such a way that an effect can be attributed to the experimental change (intervention) with sufficient probability.

However, the implementation of such field experiments is very time-consuming and often fails (of 16 intervention concepts, only four could be finalised, three others are still ongoing). Due to their dependence on third parties, the interventions often fail due to unforeseeable factors. In addition, the effects measured to date are only the results of a single experiment and require replication.

Nevertheless, this type of performance measurement is largely irreplaceable if the functioning of visitor management and guidance measures is to be evaluated. Surveys can complement intervention research very well, but generally cannot replace it.

4 Outlook

On the basis of these results, forward-looking findings can be derived for both destination practice and research.

These are the main points for research:

- Research into specific needs at the destinations. What challenges exist with regard to data-driven destination and visitor management.
- Further research should focus on the achievable effects of reservations and advance bookings. Initial data suggests an effective steering option.
- Conducting studies on the acceptance of dynamic pricing and/or digital reservation options as interventions on the part of tourism demand.
- Further research into the usability of global sensor technology for data-driven visitor management. In addition to testing new data sources, the main focus here should be on combining them with other data sources.
- Testing the effectiveness of destination dashboards: The AIR project focussed on potential visitors to destinations and how they can be reached. In the future, the aim is to research approaches that make data on visitor volumes and movements available to stakeholders in the destinations in the form of dashboards, from which steering measures can then be derived.

- Further development and implementation of the data schema developed in the AIR project in collaboration with ODTA.

The following five points are relevant to destination practice:

- Data-based destination management ("Data instead of gut feeling"): Frequency data from local and global sensor technology can help to bring more transparency to a destination's visitor flows. This transparency is necessary because destinations are predominantly public spaces with many stakeholders: Here, gut feelings can lead to false public judgements. At the same time, such data is essential if forecasts are to be calculated or alternatives proposed. In this case, gut instinct and expert knowledge are overwhelmed. *Data-driven destination management* is one of the major current trends for DMOs, and visitor flow data supports this movement, whether as part of automated management systems or as part of destination dashboards.
- Intervention and evaluation ("Show whether it really works"): The project showed that research can use field experiments to show which measures (interventions) have an effect and which do not. This knowledge is often not available; a systematic evaluation of measures does not usually take place in destination practice. This evaluation-based approach is also part of data-driven destination management and here, too, data is irreplaceable.
- Resources ("Plan enough time and money"): The project has emphatically shown that even small causes can cause major delays when obtaining data and that the data devil is in the detail. Therefore, conservative planning with sufficient time reserves and secure funding must be ensured before work begins.
- Problem selection ("select hotspots carefully"): Regardless of the specific technical design, visitor measurement and management incur costs for data acquisition (local or global sensors), data storage, influencing measures and evaluation. As a rule, these costs are best justified where a problem actually needs to be solved. In addition, a higher level of acceptance on the part of visitors can be expected there.
- Robust interventions ("Reservations instead of resignation"): It has been shown that visitors react rather sluggishly to utilisation information, if at all. It is therefore to be expected that information or nudging alone will not be able to achieve any or sufficient steering effects. Advance online reservations or bookings, on the other hand, appear to meet with a high level of acceptance and can be used to influence visitor flows.

The project team is confident that this results-based outlook will help to implement successful digital visitor management.